

Thermodynamic analysis of a tunnel biscuit oven and heat recovery system

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Abstract

Biscuit baking ovens are produced as tunnel type to reduce the cost of final product and increase the production capacity. Tunnel type ovens are designed in the form of conveyor and wire mesh or steel belt is used as a carrier element according to the biscuit type. In tunnel type biscuit ovens, the product that enters as dough from one end of the tunnel comes out as a baked product from the other end of the tunnel. In this study 1.2 m belt width and 61.5 m long tunnel oven which has 1850 kg/h Petit Beurre biscuit production capacity is analyzed. Working parameters of this tunnel oven taken into account for calculations. Natural gas is used to generate heat for baking and during baking high amount of energy released to the atmosphere with exhaust gas and water evaporated from biscuit dough. In this study, the energy and exergy analysis of the system made by taking into account the properties of flue gas discharged from industrial type biscuit oven. Flue gas released from chimney to the atmosphere is 503.15 K which could be used to generate electricity with Organic Rankine Cycle. The data obtained as a result of this study can be used to optimize the energy required to produce unit product. As a result of energy and exergy analysis of the system, 58.62 kW of power could be generated by Organic Rankine Cycle by using waste flue gas. It has been observed that energy efficiency of the oven increased from 3.90% to 11.04% and exergy efficiency of the oven increased from 0.5% to 6.22% by generating electricity with Organic Rankine Cycle.

1. Introduction

There are three important changes occurs while biscuit dough becoming biscuit. The first one is the change in the structure and texture of the biscuit dough after swelling begun, the second one is reduction of the moisture of the biscuit dough and the last one is the completion of the baking process by ensuring the color development of the biscuit [1].

Box type ovens can be classified as the most basic type of the industrial ovens. Today, most of the biscuits are baked in tunnel ovens. The biggest difference between tunnel ovens and box ovens is that biscuit dough is loaded from the one end of the tunnel and it comes out as a baked biscuit from the other end of the tunnel [2]. The production capacity of the oven is specified by means of combination of oven length (15-100 m) and oven belt with

(0,8-1,2m). Required heat to bake biscuit is provided by burner of electric heating elements positioned above and below the oven belt through the length of oven. Each oven is divided several zones, depending on its length. Each zone has its own heating elements and chimney that opens to the atmosphere. Control of tunnel ovens is done by manipulating conveyor speed (baking time) and baking temperature. Biscuit baking time usually takes less than 5 minutes and the large number of factors affect baking process and these factors make it difficult and complicated to control the oven. Therefore, baking process is usually carried out by empirical methods and baking recipes are developed by trial-and-error methods [3]. Depending on the type of biscuit, direct fired and indirect fired tunnel ovens are used in biscuit production industry. In direct fired ovens, combustion of fuel is carried out in baking chamber while in indirect fired ovens combustion of fuel takes place in combustion chamber. In indirect fired ovens, secondary air heated by the energy generated as a result of combustion which is circulated in the channels located above and below the baking chamber to control baking chamber temperature for baking biscuit. Most of the time natural gas is preferred as fuel to produce the energy required for baking process. CNG, LPG, diesel, electricity or fuel-oil can be preferred to generate baking energy where natural gas can't be supplied. Direct fired oven will be considered within the scope of this study for baking biscuit. Combustion gas in other word exhaust gas and high amount of water which is evaporated from biscuit dough during biscuit baking process, released into the atmosphere through chimney from baking chamber.

When direct flame and electric ovens are examined; product internal temperature profile, air velocity, absolute humidity and oven wall temperatures are measured for direct fired and electric ovens and heat and mass transfer parameters are calculated for each baking zone. In tunnel ovens, oven belt rotates around large drums at the entrance and exit of the oven to carry the products from one end to the other end of the oven. In the direct fired oven, gas burning elements are positioned below and above the oven belt, while in the electric ovens, the electric heating elements are positioned below and above the oven band. Each baking chamber has observation window to control baking process and a chimney that opens into the atmosphere to remove exhaust gas and steam from the baking chamber and [4].

In another study, mass and heat transfer that occurs during biscuit baking process is studied to simulate mathematical model of industrial scale biscuit oven [3].

In another study, tunnel ovens were examined in two parts. The first one is direct fired oven where gas burners or electric heater elements are positioned below and above the oven belt and the heat energy is generated in the baking chamber. The second one is the indirect fired ovens where the heat energy is generated in combustion chamber to heat the air inside the channels below and above the baking chamber to bake biscuit. In this study, 50 meters long indirect fired biscuit oven with 4 baking chambers was analyzed. Temperature and velocity of air measurements in both sides and middle sections of the oven through the length of the oven were compared with the values obtained by CFD analysis [5].

When the studies in the literature are analyzed, studies have been carried out on heat transfer to the product in tunnel biscuit ovens, the changes in product during baking and the parameters such as temperature, humidity, air velocity etc. in the baking chamber. In this study, the energy analysis of the oven will be done to evaluate heat losses, amount of energy discharged by exhaust gas and water and the efficiency of the system. By analyzing the results, studies will be carried out to reduce the lost energy and to increase the efficiency of the system by using the energy of the exhaust gas and water vapor released from the chimney to the atmosphere.

1.1. Tunnel type biscuit oven

Tunnel type ovens are the most preferred ovens in the cake production industry as they minimize energy consumption and increase production capacity. Tunnel type ovens are divided into several baking chambers through length of the oven. Temperature of bottom and above section of each baking chamber can be adjusted independently. Thus, the different temperature distribution through length of the oven and optimum baking parameters for the final product can be determined [4].

During baking, physical and biochemical changes occur in the biscuit dough such as water evaporation, blistering, hollow structure formation, shell formation, browning, starch gelatinization. Also, the heat energy is realized by radiation from the oven walls to the product surface, by convection from the hot air circulating in the oven, by conduction from the oven band to the biscuit surface, and by conduction from the biscuit surface to the biscuit core [5].

2. Material and Method

In this study, industrial type biscuit oven energy analysis will be studied and system elements will be analyzed. Energy analysis of the system assumed be a steady state. Flowchart of the biscuit oven shown in Figure 1. Point 1 refers to the oven belt entering to the system, point 2 refers to biscuit dough entering to the system and point 3 refers to the fuel entering the system that is natural gas. On the exit side of the system, point 4 is the biscuit, point 5 is the oven belt coming out of the oven, point 6 is the exhaust gas in other word combustion gas released from the chimney to the atmosphere, point 7 is the water vapor contained in the biscuit dough which is evaporated during baking process, point 8 wall losses and point 9 refers to losses and unpredicted losses as a result of inefficient combustion and oven openings. The features of the biscuit oven are given in Table 1.

2.1. Energy analysis of tunnel type oven

Kinetic energy and potential energy changes are neglected in the system. Energy balance of the system is written in Equation (1) according to the biscuit oven flow chart.

$$\dot{E}_1 + \dot{E}_2 + \dot{E}_3 = \dot{E}_4 + \dot{E}_5 + \dot{E}_6 + \dot{E}_7 + \dot{Q}_8 + \dot{Q}_9 \quad (1)$$

Figure 1. Biscuit oven flowchart.

Table 1. Properties of biscuit oven.

Description	Value
Dead State Temperature (T_0)	298.15 K
Dead State Pressure (P_0)	101.325 kPa
Relative Humidity of Oven Ambient (RH_0)	%40
Temperature of Oven Ambient (T_{Amb})	308.15 K
Moisture of Product Before Baking ($f_{water,2}$)	%22
Temperature of Product Before Baking (T_2)	308.15 K
Moisture of Product After Baking ($f_{water,4}$)	%4
Temperature of Product After Baking (T_4)	360.15 K
Fuel Type	Natural Gas
Fuel Consumption ($\dot{\vartheta}_3$)	77.6 Nm ³ /h=0.0215 m ³ /s
Quantity of Product Entering the Oven (\dot{m}_2)	2300 kg/h = 0.6389 kg/s
Chimney Gas Temperature ($T_6 = T_7$)	503.15 K
Temperature of Belt Entering the Oven (T_1)	308.15 K
Temperature of Belt Coming Out of Oven (T_5)	393.15 K
Unit Weight of Oven Belt ($m_1 = m_5$)	15 kg/m ²
Oven Belt Width (W_0)	1.2 m
Baking Chamber Length (L_0)	61.5 m
Baking Chamber Temperature (T_{bc})	503.15 K
Baking Time (t_0)	210 s
Oven Body Height ($L_{out,side}$)	1.126 m
Oven Body Width ($L_{out,bottom\&top}$)	2.003 m
Oven Out Cover Sheet Thickness (t_{cover})	0.0015 m
Insulation Thickness of Side of Baking Chamber (t_{side})	0.3 m
Insulation Thickness of Top Side of Baking Chamber (t_{top})	0.3 m
Insulation Thickness of Bottom Side of Baking Chamber (t_{bottom})	0.2 m
Baking Chamber Height ($L_{in,side}$)	0.62 m
Baking Chamber Width ($L_{in,bottom\&side}$)	0.4 m
Baking Chamber Material Thickness ($t_{chamber}$)	0.002 m

After calculating $\dot{E}_1, \dot{E}_2, \dot{E}_3, \dot{E}_4, \dot{E}_5, \dot{E}_6, \dot{E}_7$ and \dot{Q}_8 Equation (1) will be used to calculate \dot{Q}_9 .

Calculation of the energy entering to the system at point 2 and 3 calculated by Equation (2). To calculate \dot{Q}_1 and \dot{Q}_5 Equation 2 is also employed. Since the mass flow rate plays a crucial role in these calculations, Equation (3) is utilized to determine the appropriate mass flow values, which are then substituted into Equation (2) for heat transfer computations.

$$\dot{E} = \dot{m} * C * \Delta T \quad (2)$$

$$\dot{m}_{belt} = m_1 * W_0 * L_0 / t_0 \quad (3)$$

According to the information given by belt supplier, low alloy carbon steel is used as a material of belt. To calculate specific heat of oven belt at point 1, $C_{steel,1}$, and point 5, $C_{steel,5}$, Equation (4) will be used. Average temperatures ($T_{avg,1}$ and $T_{avg,5}$) are used to calculate $C_{steel,1}$ and $C_{steel,5}$ [6].

$$C_{steel} = 0.443 + 5.02 * 10^{-4} * T_{avg} - 6.667 * 10^{-7} * T_{avg}^2 + 1.202 * T_{avg}^3 \quad (4)$$

During biscuit baking process, moisture of the biscuits decreases because of evaporation of water. The amount of water and solid substances in the biscuit dough before and after baking process shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Content of petit beurre and petit beurre dough.

Content	Biscuit Dough Mass Fraction f (%)	Biscuit Mass Fraction f (%)	Point 2 (kg/s)	Point 4 (kg/s)
Protein	$f_{protein,2}$	$f_{protein,4}$	$\dot{m}_{2,protein}$ $\dot{m}_2 * f_{protein,2}$	$\dot{m}_{4,protein} = \dot{m}_{2,protein}$ $\dot{m}_4 * f_{protein,4}$
Fat	$f_{fat,2}$	$f_{fat,4}$	$\dot{m}_{2,fat}$ $\dot{m}_2 * f_{fat,2}$	$\dot{m}_{4,fat} = \dot{m}_{2,fat}$ $\dot{m}_4 * f_{fat,4}$
Carbohydrate	$f_{Carbohydrate,2}$	$f_{Carbohydrate,4}$	$\dot{m}_{2,Carbohydrate}$ $\dot{m}_2 * f_{Carbohydrate,2}$	$\dot{m}_{4,Carbohydrate} = \dot{m}_{2,Carbohydrate}$ $\dot{m}_4 * f_{Carbohydrate,4}$
Fiber	$f_{fiber,2}$	$f_{fiber,4}$	$\dot{m}_{2,fiber}$ $\dot{m}_2 * f_{fiber,2}/100$	$\dot{m}_{4,fiber} = \dot{m}_{2,fiber}$ $\dot{m}_4 * f_{fiber,4}$
Water	$f_{water,2}$	$f_{water,4}$	$\dot{m}_{2,water}$ $\dot{m}_2 * f_{water,2}$	$\dot{m}_{4,water}$ $\dot{m}_4 * f_{water,4}$

Biscuit dough and biscuit contain protein, fat, carbohydrate, fiber and water. In this study, $C_{protein}$ will be determined using Equation (5), C_{fat} using Equation (6), $C_{carbohydrate}$ using Equation (7), C_{fiber} using Equation (8), and C_{water} using Equation (9). Specific heat values of these substances vary depending temperature of these substances and Equation (10) will be used to calculate C_2 and C_4 according to film temperatures. $T_{avg,2}$ is the average temperature to calculate C_2 . $T_{avg,4}$ is the average temperature to calculate C_4 [7].

$$C_{protein} = 2.0082 + 1.2089 * 10^{-3} * T_{avg} - 1.3129 * 10^{-6} * T_{avg}^2 \quad (5)$$

$$C_{fat} = 1.9842 + 1.4733 * 10^{-3} * T_{avg} - 4.8008 * 10^{-6} * T_{avg}^2 \quad (6)$$

$$C_{carbohydrate} = 1.5488 + 1.9625 * 10^{-3} * T_{avg} - 5.9399 * 10^{-6} * T_{avg}^2 \quad (7)$$

$$C_{fiber} = 1.8459 + 1.8306 * 10^{-3} * T_{avg} - 4.6509 * 10^{-6} * T_{avg}^2 \quad (8)$$

$$C_{water} = 4.1289 - 5.3062 * 10^{-3} * T_{avg} - 9.9516 * 10^{-4} * T_{avg}^2 \quad (9)$$

Calculation of equivalent specific heats for point 2 and 4;

$$C = f_{protein} * C_{protein} + f_{fat} * C_{fat} + f_{carbohydrate} * C_{carbohydrate} + f_{fiber} * C_{fiber} + f_{water} * C_{water} \quad (10)$$

Natural gas is used as fuel in the oven. In this study, it is assumed that Russian natural gas is used as a fuel. Natural gas is a mixture of gasses which contains methane, ethane, propane and small portion of other gases. Content of Russian natural gas is shown in Table 3. which is taken into account when making calculations.

Table 3. Russian natural gas content [8].

Component	Mass Fraction (%)
Methane ($f_{methane}$)	98.52
Ethane (f_{ethane})	0.41
Propane ($f_{propane}$)	0.14
Other (f_{other})	0.93

Due to the 98% of natural gas is methane gas, the value of adiabatic flame temperature of methane gas is assumed the adiabatic flame temperature of natural gas. While T_2 is the temperature before combustion $T_{combustion} = 2223.15 K$ is the temperature just after the combustion [9].

Natural gas has reaction with combustion air to start combustion process. To calculate C_p values of natural gas and combustion air for the combustion process, average combustion temperature is $T_{avg,combustion} = 1265.65 K$ taken into account for C_p calculation.

Assuming that combustion process takes place at constant pressure and specific heat values $C_{p,air}$, $C_{p,methane}$, $C_{p,ethane}$ and $C_{p,propane}$ evaluated for combustion air, methane, ethane and propane. While calculation of $C_{p,air}$ with Equation (11), $C_{p,methane}$ with Equation (12), $C_{p,ethane}$ with Equation (13) and $C_{p,propane}$ with Equation (14), the value of θ is evaluated with $\theta = T (K)/100$ formula. Molar mass of combustion air, methane, ethane and propane can be written as

$$C_{p,air} = 28.016 + 0.19665\theta + 0.048023\theta^2 - 0.0019661\theta^3 \left(\frac{kJ}{kmol.K}\right) \quad (11)$$

$$C_{p,methane} = -672.87 + 439.74\theta^{0.25} - 24.875\theta^{0.75} - 323.88\theta^{-0.5} \left(\frac{kJ}{kmol.K}\right) \quad (12)$$

$$C_{p,ethane} = 6.895 + 17.26\theta - 0.6302\theta^2 + 0.00728\theta^3 \left(\frac{kJ}{kmol.K}\right) \quad (13)$$

$$C_{p,propane} = -4.042 + 30.46\theta - 1.571\theta^2 + 0.03171\theta^3 \left(\frac{kJ}{kmol.K}\right) \quad (14)$$

In these equations $Mr_{air} = 28.97 \text{ kg/kmol}$, $Mr_{methane} = 16.043 \text{ kg/kmol}$, $Mr_{ethane} = 30.07 \text{ kg/kmol}$, $Mr_{propane} = 44.094 \text{ kg/kmol}$ [10]. Calculation of specific heats of combustion air, methane, ethane and propane gases done with Equation (11-14), at average combustion temperature. Specific heat of natural gas evaluated with Equation (15). Assuming that specific heat of natural gas is neglected f_{other} which is shown in Table 3.

$$C_{p,ng} = f_{methane} * C_{p,methane} + f_{ethane} * C_{p,ethane} + f_{propane} * C_{p,propane} \quad (15)$$

To calculate the energy release after combustion of natural gas can be calculated by the help of Equation (16), Equation (17), Equation (18) and Equation (19) [11].

$$\sum N_{in} (\bar{h}_f^\circ + \bar{h} - \bar{h}^\circ)_{in} = \dot{Q}_3 + \sum N_{out} (\bar{h}_f^\circ + \bar{h} - \bar{h}^\circ)_{out} \quad (19)$$

$\sum N_{in}$ refers the number of moles of each reactant enter the combustion reaction and $\sum N_{out}$ refers the number of the moles each combustion products. \bar{h}_f° refers enthalpy of formation, \bar{h} refers enthalpy of reactants and products at specified state and \bar{h}° refers enthalpy of reactants and products at dead state.

The energy generated after combustion of 1 kmol natural gas, \dot{Q}_3 , evaluated by using Equation (19). The energy entering to the system from point 3 which is shown Figure 1. will be evaluated by using Equation (20).

$$\dot{E}_3 = \dot{Q}_3 \cdot (Mr_{methane} \cdot f_{methane} + Mr_{ethane} \cdot f_{ethane} + Mr_{propane} \cdot f_{propane}) \cdot \dot{m}_{ng} \quad (20)$$

The natural gas and combustion air which enters the system at 308.15 K then leaves the system from chimney at 503.15 K. Apart from the exhaust gas water vapor leaves the system from chimney at 503.15 K which is evaporated from product during baking process.

Calculation of specific heat of exhaust gas and water vapor released to the atmosphere from chimney is done at $T_{avg,exhaust}$, average exhaust temperature which is evaluated with Equation (21).

$$T_{avg,exhaust} = T_{avg,vapor} = \frac{T_2 + T_6}{2} \quad (21)$$

Calculation of specific heats of combustion air, methane, ethane and propane gases done with Equation (11-14), at average exhaust gas and vapor temperature.

Mass fraction of air and fuel can be calculated with Equation (22) as below;

$$MF = \dot{m}_{air} / \dot{m}_{ng} \quad (22)$$

Calculation of specific heat of combustion gases (mixture) with Equation (23) as below;

$$C_{p,exhaust} = C_{p,air} * MF + C_{p,ng} \quad (23)$$

The energy released to the atmosphere after combustion of 1 kmol exhaust gas, \dot{Q}_6 , evaluated by using Equation (24). The energy released from the system from point 6 which is shown in Figure 1. It will be evaluated by using Equation (25).

$$\sum N_{in} (\bar{h}_f^\circ + \bar{h} - \bar{h}^\circ)_{in} = \dot{Q}_6 + \sum N_{out} (\bar{h}_f^\circ + \bar{h} - \bar{h}^\circ)_{out} \quad (24)$$

$$\dot{E}_6 = \dot{Q}_6 \cdot (Mr_{methane} \cdot f_{methane} + Mr_{ethane} \cdot f_{ethane} + Mr_{propane} \cdot f_{propane}) \cdot \dot{m}_{ng} \quad (25)$$

The vapor released from chimney to the atmosphere at T_7 assumed as superheated water and the water inside the biscuit dough at T_2 assumed as saturated water. Enthalpy of water at point 2 and point 7 is written as h_2 ve h_7 [12].

The amount of steam released from chimney can be calculated with Equation (26) and \dot{Q}_{vapor} can be calculated with Equation (27) as below ;

$$\dot{m}_{vapor} = \dot{m}_{2,water} - \dot{m}_{4,water} \quad (26)$$

$$\dot{E}_7 = \dot{Q}_{vapor} = \dot{m}_{vapor} * (h_7 - h_2) \quad (27)$$

In order to calculate the wall losses of the biscuit oven, section view of the oven will be taken into account shown in Figure 2. To be able to evaluate wall losses equivalent thermal resistance of the oven between baking chamber and the ambient, R_{eqv} , need to be calculated.

Figure 2. Section view of biscuit oven.

Oven wall consist of three layers, Aisi 1010, rock wool and Aisi 430 from inside to outside of the layers. Thermal conductivity coefficient of the material first layer for aisi 1010 is 49.8 W/m.K [13]. Thermal conductivity coefficient of second layer for rock wool is 0.04 W/m.K and thermal conductivity coefficient of last layer for aisi 430 is 25 W/m.K [14-15].

Composite structure of the oven wall modelled in Figure 3. Equivalent thermal resistance of the oven wall, R_{eqv} , is evaluated according to Equation (28). Heat lost from each wall is evaluated with Equation (29). Sum of heat loss from walls, \dot{E}_8 , calculated according to Equation (30) [16]. Variables are needed to evaluate R_{eqv} listed in Table 4. Convection coefficient of inner and outer layer of the wall, h_{out} and h_{in} assumed to be $5 \text{ W/m}^2 \cdot \text{K}$.

$$R_{eqv} = \frac{1}{h_{out} * L_{out}} + \frac{t_{cover}}{k_{out} * L_{out}} + \frac{t_{side}}{k_{side} * 0,5 * (L_{out} + L_{in})} + \frac{t_{chamber}}{k_{chamber} * L_{in}} + \frac{1}{h_{in} * L_{in}} \quad (28)$$

$$\dot{Q}_{wall} = \frac{1}{R_{eqv}} * L_o * (T_{out} - T_{in}) \quad (29)$$

$$\dot{E}_8 = \dot{Q}_{loss, right\ wall} + \dot{Q}_{loss, left\ wall} + \dot{Q}_{loss, top\ wall} + \dot{Q}_{loss, bottom\ wall} \quad (30)$$

Figure 3. Composite Wall Equivalent Thermal Resistance [16].

Table 4. Oven parameters.

Description	Value
Protein Percentage of Product Before Baking ($f_{protein,2}$)	%6.59
Fat Percentage of Product Before Baking ($f_{fat,2}$)	%11.74
Carbohydrate Percentage of Product Before Baking ($f_{carbohydrate,2}$)	%58.22
Fiber Percentage of Product Before Baking ($f_{fiber,2}$)	%1.45
Protein Percentage of Product After Baking ($f_{protein,4}$)	%8.2
Fat Percentage of Product After Baking ($f_{fat,4}$)	%14.6
Carbohydrate Percentage of Product After Baking ($f_{carbohydrate,4}$)	%72.4
Fiber Percentage of Product After Baking ($f_{fiber,4}$)	%1.8
Convection Coefficient of Inner Layer of Wall (h_{in})	5 W/m ² .K
Convection Coefficient of Outer Layer of Wall (h_{out})	5 W/m ² .K
Oven Out Cover Thermal Conductivity Coefficient (k_{out})	25 W/m.K
Rockwool Thermal Conductivity Coefficient (k_{side})	0.04 W/m.K
Baking Chamber Material Thermal Conductivity Coefficient ($k_{chamber}$)	49.8 W/m.K
Natural Gas Mass Flowrate (\dot{m}_{ng})	0.0164 kg/s
Combustion Air Mass Flowrate (\dot{m}_{air})	0.272 kg/s
Mass Fraction of Air and Fuel (MF)	16.585

After calculating $\dot{E}_1, \dot{E}_2, \dot{E}_3, \dot{E}_4, \dot{E}_5, \dot{E}_6, \dot{E}_7$ and \dot{Q}_8 Equation (1) will be used to calculate \dot{Q}_9 . \dot{Q}_9 refers heat loss from opening of the oven, loss of inefficient combustion and unknown losses. Calculation of thermal efficiency of the system with Equation (31);

$$\eta_{th} = \frac{\dot{E}_4 - \dot{E}_2}{\dot{E}_3} \quad (31)$$

2.2. Exergy Analysis of Tunnel Type Oven

General exergy balance can be written as Equation (32);

$$\sum \dot{E}x_{in} - \sum \dot{E}x_{out} = \sum \dot{E}x_{dest} \quad (32)$$

Exergy balance of the system is written below according to the biscuit oven flow chart with Equation (33);

$$\dot{E}x_1 + \dot{E}x_2 + \dot{E}x_3 = \dot{E}x_4 + \dot{E}x_5 + \dot{E}x_6 + \dot{E}x_7 + \dot{E}x_8 + \dot{E}x_9 + \dot{E}x_{dest} \quad (33)$$

To calculate $\dot{E}x_1, \dot{E}x_2, \dot{E}x_4$ and $\dot{E}x_5$ Equation (34) can be written as [17],

$$\dot{E}x = \dot{m} * C * (T - T_0 - T_0 * \ln \frac{T}{T_0}) \quad (34)$$

Exergy of point 3 is sum of chemical exergy of natural gas and exergy of combustion air. To calculate $E x_3$ Equation (35), Equation (36), Equation (37), Equation (38) and Equation (39) can be written as [17-18];

$$E x_3 = E x_{3,ng} + E x_{3,air} \quad (35)$$

$$E x_{3,ng} = \varepsilon_{LHV} * LHV \quad (36)$$

$$\varepsilon_{LHV} = 1.033 + 0.0169 \frac{b}{a} - \frac{0.0698}{a} \quad (37)$$

$$E x_{3,ng} = f_{methane} * (\varepsilon_{LHV_{methane}} * LHV_{methane}) + f_{ethane} * (\varepsilon_{LHV_{ethane}} * LHV_{ethane}) + f_{propane} * (\varepsilon_{LHV_{propane}} * LHV_{propane}) \quad (38)$$

In Equation (38) $LHV_{methane}, LHV_{ethane}$ and $LHV_{propane}$ are 50020 kj/kg, 47480 kj/kg and 46360 kj/kg, respectively.

Lower heating values of methane, ethane and propane taken as shown in Equation (39) [19];

$$E x_{3,air} = \dot{m}_{3,air} * C_{3,air} * \left(T - T_0 - T_0 * \ln \frac{T}{T_0} \right) + R * T_0 * \ln \frac{P}{P_0} \quad (39)$$

To calculate $\dot{E}x_6$ Equation (40) can be written as [17],

$$E x_6 = \dot{m}_6 * C_6 * \left(T - T_0 - T_0 * \ln \frac{T}{T_0} \right) + R * T_0 * \ln \frac{P}{P_0} \quad (40)$$

To calculate $\dot{E}x_7$ Equation (41) can be written as [17],

$$E x_7 = \dot{m}_7 * (h_7 - h_0 - T_0 * (s_7 - s_0)) \quad (41)$$

To calculate $\dot{E}x_8$ and $\dot{E}x_9$ Equation (42) can be written as [17],

$$E x = \left(1 - \frac{T_0}{T_{sys}} \right) * Q \quad (42)$$

Exergy efficiency of the system η_{exe} can be calculated with Equation (43) shown [17],

$$\eta_{exe} = \frac{E x_4}{E x_3 + E x_2} \quad (43)$$

2.3. Waste Heat Recovery with Organic Rankine Cycle

The schematic diagram of a basic ORC system is shown in Figure 4. It includes four components; pump, heat exchanger, turbine and condenser. Huge amount of exergy is released from chimney at point 6 and point seven by means of heat. To be able to increase efficiency of the system ORC can be used to generate electricity by using the output work of turbine. The chimney flue, exhaust and vapor taken from biscuit oven goes into the heat exchanger at point 5 and leaves at point 6 in ORC which is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. ORC for heat recovery.

2.4. System Description and Modeling

The analysis of ORC system based on energy and exergy analysis. For simplicity, the following assumptions are made [20]:

- All processes are operating at steady state. Thermal losses, friction losses, kinetic energy changes and potential energy changes are neglected. Pressure drops of working fluid in heat exchanger and condenser is neglected.
- The working fluid is saturated liquid at condenser exit.
- The isentropic efficiency of turbine $\eta_{turbine}$ and the pump η_{pump} are 0.8.
- The efficiency of the heat exchanger η_{hex} and the condenser η_{cond} are 0.85.
- The efficiency of the electricity generator η_{gen} is 0.95.
- The minimum temperature difference ΔT_{pp} in heat exchanger is 15 K.
- Turbine inlet temperature is taken 15 K lower than the temperature of hot fluid.
- The inlet temperature of hot fluid in heat exchanger is 503.15 K.
- The pressures of working fluid are taken 1000 kPa at the inlet of turbine, 10 kPa at the outlet of the turbine.

2.5. Energy and Exergy Analysis of Waste Heat Recovery Cycle

R113 is selected as the working fluid. Thermodynamic properties of R113 is taken from "NIST Reference Fluid Thermodynamic and Transport Properties-REFPROP Version 8.0". The equation for energy and exergy analysis of the system are listed below.

Process 1-2 (Pump) with Equation (44), Equation (45), Equation (46) and Equation (47);

$$\dot{W}_{pump} = \dot{m}_{wf} * (h_2 - h_1) = \dot{m}_{wf} * (h_{2s} - h_1) / \eta_{pump} \quad (44)$$

$$\dot{E}x_1 = \dot{m}_{wf} * (h_1 - h_0 - T_0(s_1 - s_0)) \quad (45)$$

$$\dot{E}x_2 = \dot{m}_{wf} * (h_2 - h_0 - T_0(s_2 - s_0)) \quad (46)$$

$$\dot{E}x_{d,pump} = \dot{E}x_1 - \dot{E}x_2 + \dot{W}_{pump} \quad (47)$$

Process 2-3,5-6 (Heat Exchanger) with Equation (48), Equation (49) and Equation (50);

$$\dot{Q}_e = \dot{m}_5 * c_5 * \Delta T_{5-6} = \dot{m}_{wf} * (h_3 - h_2) / \eta_{hex} \quad (48)$$

$$\dot{E}x_3 = \dot{m}_{wf} * (h_3 - h_0 - T_0(s_3 - s_0)) \quad (49)$$

$$\dot{E}x_{d,heat\ exchanger} = \dot{E}x_2 - \dot{E}x_3 + \dot{Q}_e * \left(1 - \frac{T_0}{(T_5 + T_6)/2}\right) \quad (50)$$

Process 3-4 (Turbine) with Equation (51), Equation (52), Equation (53) and Equation (54);

$$\dot{W}_{turbine} = \dot{m}_{wf} * (h_3 - h_4) = \dot{m}_{wf} * (h_3 - h_{4s}) * \eta_{turbine} \quad (51)$$

$$\dot{W}_{gen} = \eta_{gen} * \dot{W}_{turbine} \quad (52)$$

$$\dot{E}x_4 = \dot{m}_{wf} * (h_4 - h_0 - T_0(s_4 - s_0)) \quad (53)$$

$$\dot{E}x_{d,turbine} = \dot{E}x_3 - \dot{E}x_4 - \dot{W}_{turbine} \quad (54)$$

Process 4-1,7-8 (Condenser) with Equation (55) and Equation (56);

$$\dot{Q}_L = \dot{m}_{wf} * (h_4 - h_1) = \dot{m}_{cw} * (h_8 - h_7) \quad (55)$$

$$\dot{E}x_{d,condenser} = \dot{E}x_4 - \dot{E}x_1 + \dot{Q}_L * \left(1 - \frac{T_0}{(T_4 + T_1)/2}\right) \quad (56)$$

Network output with Equation (57);

$$\dot{W}_{net} = \dot{W}_{gen} - \dot{W}_{pump} \quad (57)$$

Thermal efficiency with Equation (58);

$$\eta_{th} = \frac{\dot{W}_{net}}{\dot{Q}_e} \quad (58)$$

Exergy efficiency with Equation (59);

$$\eta_{exe} = \frac{\dot{W}_{net}}{\dot{Q}_e * (1 - 2 * T_0 / (T_5 + T_6))} \quad (59)$$

3. Results

Analysis of the system is divided in two sections. In first section, biscuit oven energy and exergy analysis is carried out. In the second section energy and exergy analysis of ORC is carried out.

3.1. Results of Biscuit Oven Thermodynamical Analysis

The comments presented in the literature were guiding for this study. The actual working parameters of an analyzed baking oven in Table 4. Volumetric air fuel ratio (A/F) for the combustion of natural gas is assumed to be 11. Inlet pressure of natural gas is 180 mbar and the inlet temperature of the natural gas is 35 °C. Density of natural gas for 180 mbar at 35 °C is $\rho_{ng} = 0.762 \text{ kg/m}^3$ (Density of Natural Gas). Density of combustion air for 35 °C and 101.325 kPa is $\rho_{air} = 1.145 \text{ kg/m}^3$ [19]. Natural gas consumption found 0.0164 kg/s and consumption of combustion air found 0.282 kg/s.

As a result of the calculations; 24.12 kW energy goes into the system from nodal point 1 with oven belt, 15.04 kW energy goes into the system from nodal point 2 with biscuit dough, 820.58 kW energy goes into the system

from nodal point 3 with natural gas and combustion air, 47.05 kW energy comes out from the system from nodal point 4 with baked biscuit, 214.15 kW energy comes out from the system from nodal point 5 with oven belt, 67.42 kW energy comes out from the system from nodal point 6 with exhaust gas from chimney, 337.64 kW energy comes out from the system from nodal point 7 with vapor from chimney, totally 405.06 kw energy released from chimney to the atmosphere, 8.98 kW energy comes out from system from point 8 with wall loss and 184.79 kW energy comes out from system from point 9 with unknown loss. Thermal efficiency of the system is found 3.9 according to calculation.

As a result of the calculations; 0.396 kW exergy goes into the system from nodal point 1 with oven belt, 0.247 kW exergy goes into the system from nodal point 2 with biscuit dough, 1024.53 kW exergy goes into the system from nodal point 3 with natural gas and combustion air, 5.13 kW exergy comes out from the system from nodal point 4 with baked biscuit, 31.58 kW energy comes out from the system from nodal point 5 with oven belt, 16.108 kW exergy comes out from the system from nodal point 6 with exhaust gas from chimney, 119.537 kW exergy comes out from the system from nodal point 7 with vapor from chimney, totally 135.65 kW exergy released from chimney to the atmosphere, 3.66 kW exergy comes out from system from point 8 with wall loss and 75.29 kW exergy comes out from system from point 9 with unknown loss. Exergy efficiency of the system is found 0.5% according to calculation.

3.2. Results of ORC Analysis

Exhaust gas and vapor is released to the atmosphere from chimney of the oven. To be able to increase the efficiency of the system, heat energy of chimney flue is converted into electricity energy by ORC.

As a result of calculation; 3.54 kW energy is consumed by pump to increase the pressure of working fluid. 65.43 kW energy is generated by turbine and 62.16 kW electricity produced by electricity generator. Net output work is evaluated 58.623 kW. The energy efficiency and exergy efficiency of the ORC is calculated as 18.52% and 56.65% respectively. Thermodynamic parameters of nodal points and heat transfer values shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Thermodynamic Parameters of Nodal Points and Heat Transfer Values.

Points	T (K)	P (kPa)	\dot{m} (kg/s)	h (kJ/kg)	c (kJ/kgK)	Q (kW)	Ex (kW)
1	308.15	101.3	5.271	138.70	0.458	-	0.396
2	308.15	101.3	0.6389	713.62	2.354	-	0.247
3	308.15	119.3	$\dot{m}_{3,ng}$	$h_{3,ng}$	$c_{3,ng}$	-	$Ex_{3,air}$
			0.0164	6324.60	5.017		177.330
			$\dot{m}_{3,air}$	$h_{3,air}$	$c_{3,air}$		$Ex_{ch,ng}$
			0.282	1487.71	1.181		846.720
3	308.15	119.3	\dot{m}_3	h_3	c_3	-	Ex_3
			0.2986	1753.83	1.391		1024.053
4	360.15	101.3	0.51375	588.50	1.761	-	5.130
5	393.15	101.3	5.271	167.60	0.478	-	31.580
6	503.15	101.3	$\dot{m}_{6,ng}$	$h_{6,ng}$	1.102	-	16.108
			0.0164	1023.61			
			$\dot{m}_{6,air}$	$h_{6,air}$			
			0.282	412.69			
6	503.15	101.3	\dot{m}_6	h_6	-	-	-
			0.2886	446.85			
7	503.15	101.3	0.125	2802.90	-	-	119.54
8	-	-	-	-	-	8.98	3.66
9	-	-	-	-	-	184.79	75.29

Thermodynamic parameters of nodal points for ORC shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Thermodynamic parameters of nodal points for ORC.

Points	T (K)	P (kPa)	\dot{m} (kg/s)	h (kJ/kg)	s (kJ/kgK)	c (kJ/kgK)
0	298.15	101.325	1.275	222.690	1.0793	-
1	305.78	60	1.275	229.710	1.1026	-
2	307.51	3500	1.275	232.485	1.1044	-
3	498.15	3500	1.275	480.730	1.7038	-
4	378.26	60	1.275	429.426	1.7385	-
5	503.15		0.424			4.863
6	322.51		0.424			4.863
$\eta_{turbine}$				0.80		
η_{pump}				0.80		
η_{hex}				0.85		
η_{cond}				0.85		
η_{gen}				0.95		

4. Discussion

Specific heat of the biscuit is 1.75 kJ/kgK in literature [21], calculation of the specific heat of the biscuit with respect to biscuit content confirms the value found in the literature 1501.7 kJ energy needed for baking 1 kg biscuit. When the nodal points of the system are examined, 3.90% of inlet energy used to increase the temperature of biscuit dough to the temperature of the biscuit comes out of oven, 23.15% of inlet energy used to increase the temperature of oven belt comes out of oven, 8.21% of inlet energy is released from chimney with exhaust gases, 41.13% of the inlet energy released from chimney with water evaporated from product, 0.45% of the inlet energy is lost from wall of the oven, 22.51% of inlet energy is found to be unknown loss. Thermal efficiency of the system is calculated as 3.90%.

To be able to reduce the energy need for biscuit baking, energy transfer in system boundary needs to be minimized. According to calculation, 405.06 kW energy in other word 49.35% of produced energy is released from chimney to the atmosphere at 503.15 K. Reducing the temperature of the product (360.15 K) at the exit of the oven reduces \dot{E}_4 value. The energy needed to heat the oven belt can be reduced by increasing the temperature of the oven belt before entering the oven that can be done by insulating the area where oven belt travels from exit of the oven to entrance of the oven which reduces \dot{E}_1 . Also, lighter wire mesh belt can be preferred to bake biscuit to be able to reduce the energy needed for heating the oven belt. If the exit temperature of oven belt reduced, \dot{E}_5 would be reduced. By reducing baking temperature, exhaust and vapor temperature can be reduced in other word \dot{E}_6 and \dot{E}_7 can be reduced. So, the energy released from chimney to the atmosphere can be reduced. Addition of the comment above, by reducing the amount of water in biscuit dough, the amount of energy needed to evaporate water from dough can be reduced. To reduce insulation loss, \dot{Q}_8 , thickness of the insulation can be increased to reduce heat losses from walls also insulator with less thermal conductivity could be used for insulation of the oven. To reduce unknown loses, \dot{Q}_9 , special precaution could be taken into account for heat loss from oven openings and increasing the burning efficiency of natural gas burner could be taken into account.

Additional of above comments exhaust gas and vapor energy released from chimney can be used in the production of electrical energy by passing the air through an ORC. By generating electricity with ORC increase the

thermal efficiency of the biscuit oven changes from 3.90% to 11.04% and exergy efficiency of the biscuit oven changes from 0.5% to 6.22%.

5. Conclusion

In this study, the energy distribution and efficiency of a biscuit baking system were analyzed, and potential improvements were identified. The findings indicate that a significant portion of the input energy is lost through exhaust gases, water vapor, and unidentified losses, resulting in a low thermal efficiency of 3.90%. To enhance efficiency, strategies such as reducing the product's exit temperature, preheating the oven belt, optimizing insulation, and lowering the baking temperature were proposed. Additionally, utilizing waste heat through an ORC could significantly improve system performance, increasing thermal efficiency to 11.04% and exergy efficiency to 6.22%. These optimizations demonstrate a viable approach to reducing energy consumption and improving the sustainability of biscuit production.

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Author contributions

Murat Erdoğan: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Writing-Reviewing and Editing.

Merve Şentürk Acar: Data curation, Writing-Original draft preparation, Software, Validation.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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